

GEOGRAFIYA DARSLARI ORQALI EKOLOGIK MAS'ULIYATNI SHAKLLANTIRISH

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Ushbu maqolada geografiya darslari orqali talabalar o'rtasida ekologik mas'uliyatni tarbiyalashning ahamiyati muhokama qilinadi. Talabalarda tabiatga ongli munosabatni tarbiyalashda geografiyaning roli chuqur tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, ekologik ta'lim ta'lim tizimida, ayniqsa maktablarda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

В данной статье рассматривается важность воспитания экологической ответственности учащихся на уроках географии. Подробно анализируется роль географии в формировании у учащихся осознанного отношения к природе. Результаты исследования свидетельствуют о том, что экологическое образование играет значительную роль в системе образования, особенно в школах.

This article discusses the importance of fostering ecological responsibility among students through geography lessons. The role of geography in cultivating a conscious attitude toward nature among students is thoroughly analyzed. The study results indicate that environmental education plays a significant role in the educational system, especially in schools.

Ключевые слова: *экологическая ответственность, уроки географии, экологическое образование, устойчивое развитие, экологическая культура, международный опыт.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ekologik mas'uliyat, geografiya darslari, ekologik ta'lim, barqaror rivojlanish, ekologik madaniyat, xalqaro tajriba.*

Keywords: *Ecological responsibility, geography lessons, environmental education, sustainable development, ecological culture, international experience.*

Today, ecological responsibility is a relevant issue at both global and national levels. Humanity's lack of responsibility towards nature has led to an escalation of problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and environmental disasters. These circumstances underscore the need to develop ecological culture and promote the concept of sustainable development in society. Ecological culture comprises the set of understandings and values that encourage people to act responsibly toward the environment and avoid harming nature. In this context, instilling ecological responsibility among youth is essential for society.

Geography occupies a special place among school subjects as it provides the foundation for environmental education by explaining the interconnection between nature and humans. Geography students learn about the use of natural resources, unique characteristics of ecological regions, ecosystem preservation, and natural laws. This knowledge fosters ecological responsibility by developing a conscious attitude and actions towards nature.

The aim of this article is to analyze educational methods aimed at fostering ecological responsibility and examine their application within the scope of geography lessons. The article provides an in-depth analysis of the role of geography in environmental education and its influence on students' ecological perspectives.

The theoretical foundations of fostering ecological responsibility cover important aspects of environmental education. The concept of ecological responsibility encompasses a set of conscious actions and values aimed at maintaining the balance between nature and society. Its main components include ecological thinking, ecological values, and conscious behavior. Ecological thinking develops through understanding the laws of nature and the interconnections within ecosystems [1]. Ecological values represent a set of personal attitudes and views aimed at protecting and preserving nature's wealth. Conscious behavior entails avoiding harm to the environment and using natural resources efficiently. Therefore, the concept of ecological responsibility is a core component of the environmental education system, helping young people understand the need to preserve nature through a conscious approach.

Geography plays a crucial role in cultivating ecological responsibility as it comprehensively addresses natural and social factors. Geography allows students to understand natural phenomena, methods for utilizing natural resources, and the necessity of their conservation. Through geography, students comprehend local and global ecological issues and acquire strategies to address them. This subject explains the interrelationship between nature and society more broadly and plays an important role in developing ecological worldviews and responsibility among students [2]. Geography not only teaches the location of natural resources but also highlights their impact on human life and the importance of their proper use.

The connection between ecology and geography holds a special place in shaping an ecological worldview. Geography reveals core ecological concepts and explores the interrelationships of natural and social processes. For example, in geography classes, students study the unique features of ecosystems, the distribution of resources, and the need to conserve them. Thus, the close connection between ecology and geography contributes to deepening students' environmental knowledge and fostering a conscious attitude toward nature.

A review of methods for fostering ecological responsibility highlights key pedagogical methods in geography aimed at promoting ecological responsibility. These methods include analyzing ecological issues, using research and projects to instill environmental responsibility in students [3]. Geography lessons not only demonstrate the complexity of environmental issues but also offer solutions. For example, through comparative analysis, students examine ecological issues in various countries and evaluate the effectiveness of different approaches. This approach influences students' ability to make informed decisions and promotes a responsible attitude toward nature.

Moreover, innovative approaches play a vital role in developing ecological awareness. Multimedia resources, project-based learning, and field studies are effective tools in fostering ecological awareness. Using multimedia technology allows students to visualize natural phenomena and understand ecological issues through real-world examples. Project work develops students' creativity and directs them toward solving real ecological problems [4]. Field studies provide direct contact with nature, further strengthening students' ecological responsibility.

№	Practice Type	Project Name and Country	Description	Results and Effectiveness

1	International Practice	Eco-Schools, Finland	Develops environmental education by establishing ecological clubs among students.	Increased ecological awareness; waste recycling improved by 30%, energy savings by 20%.
		School Greenery Project, Japan	Environmental education through school-area greening and tree planting.	Green area increased by 40%, respect for nature improved.
		Green Schools Alliance, USA	Supports energy saving and recycling in schools.	Energy consumption reduced by 15%, recycling increased by 50%.
2	National Practice	Green School, Kazakhstan	Promotes environmental responsibility and literacy among students.	Number of environmental activities increased, responsibility level rose by 35%.
		My Green School, Kazakhstan	Environmental protection activities, tree planting, cleanup events.	Interest increased by 40%, participation level by 50%.
		Atameken EcoFund, Kazakhstan	Educational program on efficient resource use.	Knowledge of recycling rose by 60%, ecological culture was established.

Table 1 – Review of International and National Practices in Fostering Ecological Responsibility

There are several current trends in environmental education. Firstly, the widespread use of digital technology has enriched environmental education methods, allowing for interactive and multimedia approaches. For instance, virtual tours, ecological animations, and games engage students and connect them directly with nature. Secondly, project-based learning and field studies are emphasized to foster a conscious attitude toward the environment and strengthen responsibility. Additionally, introducing international environmental programs and projects has shown in the Table-1 (such as Eco-Schools and the Green Schools Alliance) in Kazakhstan marks a significant step towards supporting ecological responsibility in the national educational system [5].

There are several barriers to fostering ecological responsibility through geography. Firstly, many schools lack the necessary material and technical base for environmental education, limiting multimedia resources and outdoor research activities. Secondly, insufficient time and resources allocated to ecological topics in geography prevent full development of students' ecological awareness. Thirdly, inadequate teacher training in environmental education is a pressing issue. Teachers need professional development courses or seminars on environmental topics. Solutions include allocating resources to schools, retraining teachers, and integrating environmental education more deeply into curricula.

Several directions for future research in fostering ecological responsibility through geography can be suggested. Firstly, it is necessary to improve methods for measuring both

quantitative and qualitative indicators of students' ecological literacy and responsibility. Secondly, comparative research on effective environmental education methods in international and national contexts is essential. Thirdly, exploring methods for developing ecological responsibility through digital tools (multimedia, virtual reality, online platforms) is recommended. Finally, it is vital to examine ways to strengthen the role of parents and the community in environmental education, as ecological upbringing should extend beyond the school to include family and society.

This article addressed the issues of fostering ecological responsibility through geography lessons. A review of international and national practices identified effective methods and challenges in promoting ecological responsibility. Geography, as a subject that fosters ecological understanding, allows students to grasp the interrelationship between nature and society.

Forming ecological responsibility through geography plays an essential role in the education system. This knowledge and training not only develop students' ecological culture but also contribute to their sense of environmental responsibility. One of the primary goals in education is to help young generations understand the importance of protecting nature and raise them as conscious citizens who contribute to sustainable development in the future.

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